

CORRECT PLACED AND CORRECT NOT PLACED ISSUES .

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ANNOTATION.

In the article The correctness of the generalized solutions of direct and inverse problems to the heat equation is studied.

Key words : Correct and incorrect issues , Adamar examples , metric spaces , Laplace equation , t ' right problem , narrow oscillation equation

ANNOTATION.

The dissertation "Non local boundary conditional direct and inverse problems in an unbounded domain for the heat propagation in three-dimensional space" is one of the important sections of mathematics. Interest in this field is determined by the theoretical significance of the obtained results and their practical applications.

Enter

Mathematician of physics very many problems private derivative equations in the form of description can be. Such in description to him suitable was. borderline issues the solution natural determination opportunity there is and that's it with together , them to solve known methods apply can. In nature occurring processes fraction in order equations more precisely expression is enough For now come them practical to issues increased demand for education because of research increased and of issues to be placed accuracy including specialists _ to the front Entirely new type issues was put

Mathematician physics of their problems in the laying some functions (initial , boundary conditions) participation reaches : placed of the matter the solution that's it to functions depends will be These functions are usually experimental _ based on is determined , therefore for them too absolute sure to find possible it's not .

So starter and borderline in the conditions everyone time something of error to be it is inevitable . This is an error own in turn also influence the solution does _ Primary and borderline issues in checking , of the solution existence and from its uniqueness except initial and borderline in the conditions placed of error to the solution how effect to do identification is also important to the point has _

Checking issue $-M$ through set we can Any $_M$ of the matter essence given $\varphi \in E_\varphi$ to functions basically $u \in E_u$ the solution from finding consists of this on E_u the ground and E_φ - metrics ρ_u and ρ_φ has been some kind of metric spaces . These spaces of the matter put with is determined $.M$ of the matter the solution concept determined being , each $\varphi \in E_\varphi$ unique $u = R(\varphi) \in E_u$ to the element solution suitable come _

If optional $\varepsilon > 0$ for so $\delta(\varepsilon) > 0$ number show possible being _ $\rho_\varphi(\varphi_1, \varphi_2) \leq \delta(\varepsilon)$ from inequality $\rho_u(u_1, u_2) \leq \varepsilon$ inequality come If , M the problem is (E_u, E_φ) spaces in pairs is called a stationary problem .

In this $u_i = R(\varphi_i)$, $u_i \in E_u$, $\varphi_i \in E_\varphi$, $i = 1, 2, \dots$ of the matter the solution given conditions (initial and borderline terms , of Eq coefficients , free term and hk) to continuously depends will be

If being investigated M for the issue this

1) optional $\varphi \in E_\varphi$ for $u \in E_u$ solution there is ;

2) u the solution is unique;

3) problem (E_u, E_φ) spaces in pairs steady conditions if fulfilled , M the problem is (E_u, E_φ) spaces in pairs correctly placed _ _ _ or straight away is called a correct problem .

Aks the issue is correct is called an open question , i.e this without above from requirements at least one can't be done .

That thing emphasizing let's go , correct definition of the problem given (E_u, E_φ) to the pair is relevant because another in metrics that's it of the parable himself correct placed it can be .

Correct not placed issues .

Koshy-Kovalevskaya theorem , his generality to the description have that regardless differential the normal system of Eq for Koshi issue correct that it is placed full solution does not

Indeed , it is solution of the torema problem enough small in the field there is and unity supply is enough Usually , it is the evidence from the beginning given (in general small non) fields right that display is required . From this except , of Eq free Come on and initial terms , in general in fact , analytical didn't happen functions will be

Finally , a solution initial to the conditions continuously depends it may not be . This proof pointer example the first times People by Created .

1) **People example** . This

$$\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} = 0$$

Laplace of Eq $y > 0$ half in the plain

$$u(x,0) = 0, \quad u_y(x,0) = e^{-\sqrt{k}} \cos kx$$

initial conditions satisfactory regular the solution be found By checking to see difficult not that _ of the matter one by one the solution

$$u(x,y) = \frac{1}{k} e^{-\sqrt{k}} \cos kx \operatorname{sh} ky, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots$$

in appearance will be

if $k \rightarrow +\infty$, $e^{-\sqrt{k}} \cos kx$ function to zero flat tends to, $e^{-\sqrt{k}} \cos kx = 0$, but $u(x,y)$ solution from scratch different optional y at

$$u(x,y) = \frac{1}{k} e^{-\sqrt{k}} \cos kx \cdot \operatorname{sh} ky \rightarrow 0, \quad k \rightarrow +\infty$$

will be

Laplace equation for Koshi issue correct it is an unanswered question .

2)

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2}$$

heat permeability of Eq $t < 0$, $0 \leq x \leq \pi$ in the field

$$u(x,0) = \frac{1}{k} e^{-\sqrt{k}} \sin kx, \quad u(0,t) = u(\pi,t) = 0$$

conditions satisfactory the solution be found

this matter the solution

$$u(x,t) = e^{-\sqrt{k}} e^{k^2 t} \sin kx$$

from fuchsia consists of

Naturally each k for his own initial condition and to him suitable didn't happen there is a solution . That's why it was written the solution solutions view as a sequence need _

$e^{-\sqrt{k}} \sin kx$ function to $k \rightarrow \infty$ zero at tends to, but solution while just like that People as an example never how to the limit does not strive

3) Narrow swing equation

$$\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} - \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} = 0$$

for Directly the issue we don't check

$0 < x < \pi$, $0 < y < \alpha \pi$ in a rectangle ,

$$u(0, y) = 0, u(\pi, y) = 0, 0 \leq y \leq \alpha \pi$$

$$u(x, 0) = 0, u(x, \alpha \pi) = \frac{\sin kx}{\sqrt{k}}, 0 \leq x \leq \pi$$

conditions a satisfyingly narrow swing of Eq the solution be found Here α - positive an irrational number.

of the matter the solution

$$u(x, y) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{k}} \frac{\sin kx \sin ky}{\sin k \alpha \pi}, k = 1, 2, \dots$$

with the formula is determined .

Ravshanki $k \rightarrow \infty$ borderline at conditional $\frac{\sin kx}{\sqrt{k}}$ function to zero strives _

Thighs from theory as it is known p_k and q_k whole numbers sequence _ _ there is is any α for an irrational number

$$\left| \alpha - \frac{p_k}{q_k} \right| < \frac{1}{q_k^2}$$

from inequalities appropriate will be

Based on this

$$|\sin q_k \alpha \pi| = |\sin(q_k \alpha - p_k) \pi| < \frac{\pi}{q_k}$$

inequality harvest we ca n't

this case , under investigation of the matter the solution $u(x, y)$ function for

$$|u(x, y)| = \left| \frac{1}{\sqrt{q_k}} \frac{\sin q_k x \sin q_k y}{\sin q_k \alpha \pi} \right| > \frac{\sqrt{q_k}}{\pi} |\sin q_k x \sin q_k y|$$

to inequality have we will be

A narrower swing than that equation for Direchle issue correct not an open question the fact that come comes out.

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